

Cultural Disillusionment and Loosing Innocence: A Comparative Study of American Identity ‘Abroad’ and at ‘Home’ in Daisy Miller and The Catcher in the Rye

Metali Akter

BA (Hons) Student of English Department, University of Information Technology and Sciences, (UITS)
Bangladesh, Dhaka

Mail: trishametali@gmail.com

Abstract:

The study of this research paper portraits of, “Cultural Disillusionment and Loosing Innocence: A Comparative Study of American Identity Abroad and at Home in Daisy Miller and The Catcher in the Rye” by Henry James and J.D Salinger. The research explores the theme of navigating the transition from innocence to experience which is present in both text. Daisy Miller, initially contracts American and European societies, highlighting the situation between innocence and societal expectations while The Catcher in the Rye focuses on teenagers disillusionment with “phoniness” of the adult world and the struggle focused upon childhood innocence. The novella Daisy Miller showcase class distinct, misjudged by European culture and breakdown of innocence in a very short time, while The Catcher in the Rye illustrated, traumatic moments of a young boy, who want to stay in the catcher of the rye and all, also suffering from depression, misjudged by society, breakdown of innocence, cultural disillusionment and again cope up with terrible consequences. The Miller family misjudged when they are traveling by the people like Mrs. Costello and Mrs. Walker, and they were representing two distinct classes in American society. Henry James thus exposes the role of the ideas about class and social standing play in upper-class American society and they has shape their dealings with one another. On the contrary, The Catcher in the Rye by JD Salinger tries to find out the Holden Caulfield’s complexities of an adulthood and the world around him. The loss of his innocence and the pain of growing up from childhood to adulthood. Holden does not meticulous analysis of the people. The author shows the relationship through the characters and theme. The study used a qualitative research method. This research is concerned with quality of information. This paper is discussed by rating text as a primary source of information. Paper, journal reports are used to as a secondary source of information. This paper is also processed in a set of comparative way and many library theories are used for instant alienation, identify crisis, social judgment, teenagers disillusionment with phoniness and cultural conflict to analyze the study broadly and critically.

Keywords: *Alienation, teenagers, disillusionment, phoniness, grappling, cultural conflict, Hypocrisy, Navigation, innocence.*

1. Introduction

American parents roles toward their children were often careless. They rarely expressed affection openly to their children, and their love was mostly shown through providing basic needs rather than through physical or verbal warmth. In 19th century American industrialization transformed family life horrible, and quarrels between parents became more common. These conflicts had a deeply negative impact on the children. Witnessing frequent arguments created emotional stress, trauma, fear, anxiety and insecurity in their young minds. Parenting styles became negligent and passive. There were lack of complete absence of proper discipline and guidance.

On the other hand, American literature distinguishes itself from European traditions by embracing unique forms of intellectual freedom. Through specialized programs and a foundation in literature, it cultivates an independent cultural identity. Unlike Europe or England, American writers draw from

their own widespread experiences on foreign soil, shaping a distinct literary ethos. This "code – than make it up great again" flourishing American literature. So that, they will write for their own intellectual culture rather than depend on other scholars culture, education, society and even politics as well. As a result, American literature prioritizes self-reliant intellectual culture over dependence on external influences.

This American novella *Daisy Miller* and novel *The Catcher in the Rye*, these two are purely authentic literature. These two text are purely represents the American society and life after the revolution and their values as well. A true American Daisy Miller, when went to Europe, how did she misjudged by the European. Again Holden Caulfield misjudged at home and no need to go anywhere. For that reason, Daisy Miller struggled more than Holden. Because Holden facing the trauma, anxieties, sufferings and everything in his own home. Both suffer in different ways but their suffering is actually in spite of social pressures.

Daisy Miller is a famous novella by Henry James, deals a lack of parents guidance, discipline and more than societal misjudgment in American society. It is published in 1878 during the 19th century. The story reflects that time when industrialization and urbanization were transforming into family dynamics. For example Mrs. Miller does not prevent Daisy from going outside alone with the men whom she knew recently but not deeply, including her controversial outing with Mr. Giovanelli in Rome. Ultimately lack of supervision leads Daisy's social misjudgment. Furthermore, Mrs. Costello and Mrs. Walker also misjudged Daisy as a "uncultured" and a "flirtatious girl" as well.

On the other hand, Holden Coalfield is typically modern, his is a aggressive boy, who is just seventeen years old. Holden's mental health struggles reflect lack of focus on children's emotional needs. The famous novel "*The Catcher in the Rye*" is written by J.D Salinger, who show the result of familial and institutional hypocrisy. Over the time many children has developed their behavioral issues, becoming either aggressive or withdrawn. This problems increases from family conflicts and parental quarrel and giving a negative impact to their children as Holden has deal with it.

Daisy in *Daisy Miller* in 1878, the innocent girl who lost her innocence and became experienced through judgment by another cultures people. The story changed with misjudgments of Daisy by Mrs. Costello and Mrs Walker. When Daisy joined Rome party with her friend Mr. Giovanelli, her behavior has been criticized by a woman. Mrs Miller dismisses the situation with rumor by stating that, "She is very fond of society and it's so very dull for her there." In that initial part, Daisy the protagonist lost her innocence which is focused. American strategies became difficult and cause of protagonist's loosing sing innocence. Furthermore, Daisy don't wants to capture American culture but the fashionable sense of the era find her "Uncultured" and fall her into a emotional breakdown. Another part of loosing innocence by Winterbourne's aunt, the Miller family is "Nouveau riche" means they are newly rich and had lack of "old money" graces. European society's harsh judgment is the actual worst reason for Daisy's loosing innocence. On the contrary Holden, who being abused by his teacher, who is portrait as a disgraceful character. Holden Caulfield lost his innocence in the novel, for not a single event but a gradual erosion. He see the adults as liars and the starting point was from his Shallow classmates to his double face teacher Mr. Antolini. His idealized memory of Jane Gallagher contrasts with Stradlater's physical exploitation with her tainting Holden's last tie to childhood purity. Another reason is caused for loosing the innocence is, starting smoking in dorm and the trauma of his own life. He was far away from his family and taught what he saw and became aggressive. He fights with his class mate which is the breakdown of his innocence as well.

The Catcher in the Rye, was first published in 1940 and it is divided into twenty six parts of S.D Salingers novel. It defines the postwar American disillusionment and the alienation of a generation caught between childhood authenticity. "Phoniness as a Disease" captures how Holden sees much of the adult world in his early age. He realized that his surroundings are covered with fake people and obsessed with appearances. Institution of Penny prep here symbolized the whole system that, prioritize reputation or flattering rich parents over the truth. The American at home represent how a children

being abused like Holden Caulfield. The situation based on cultural disillusionment, where the younger generation like Holden struggles to find meaning, honesty and identity in the world that often feels fake. His inner conflict and rejection of social conformity which he sees as corrupted. On the other hand, Daisy Miller 1878, a four part serially novella. The novella find cultural disillusionment in the American identity in abroad. The word “uncultured” represent the cultural disillusionment of the protagonist Daisy. Daisy Miller being criticized by European wealthy widow with jealousy Mrs. Costello. Daisy is not only judged by dresses but also “Nouveau riche” stands for being newly reach. Mrs Costello and Mrs Walker criticized, while Miller Family in Europe. James critiques cultural hypocrisy of American vs Europe. Mrs Walker publicly shames Daisy cutting her off society because she danced with her friend .Yet the society punished Daisy more harshly as like she is genuinely a corrupted finger. Cultural clash represent the independent naive, spirit of Daisy. She believes in freedom and sincerity but European sees her as a vulgar. Although she is proud of being an American as well. She has not any fear about the society as well as their any harsh words.

When any character developed, build or evolve psychological, the type of literature is called Bildungsroman. After American revolution this literary genre actually flourished in American literary pieces. Bildungsroman is a psychological and moral growth and change of the protagonist from childhood to adulthood . Although the Bildungsroman first arose in Germany, it had extensive influence first in Europe and later throughout the world. Usually it is the beginning of the story, there is an emotional loss which makes the protagonist leave on their journey. In a bildungsroman, the goal is maturity and the protagonist achieved it gradually and with lots of difficulty. The genre often feature a main conflict between the main character and society. Typically, the values of society are gradually accepted by the protagonist’s mistakes and disappointments are over. In some works the protagonist is able to reach out the situation and help others after having maturity.

Psychologically both Daisy Miller and Holden Caulfield represent their thoughts. Daisy Miller who protect her family from the harshness of Europeans. She actually took all the blame given by abroad people just to save her family. Initially that part proved the girl Daisy as a psychological balanced girl. Moreover Holden Caulfield protect his sister Phoebe Coalfield, whom he admires and respect deeply. Phoebe represents innocence, authenticity and unconditional love in the Holden’s eyes. Holden wants to protect her because he don’t want that the society play the same role or incident with her. For that reason, also Holden keeps his psychological balance.

Daisy has been destroyed by others judgment ; Holden is tormented by his own disillusionment. These both text explores the failures of American parenting across these two characters. Also examines how Henry James and J.D Salinger use their protagonists downfalls to challenge the values of their respective or innocence to experience time. According to literary critique when parents were unaware of their duty to their children and protect them, their children becomes casualties of societal expectation, cultural disillusionment, clashes and their innocence.

Table of Contents

Serial No -	Contents	Page No -
1.	Introduction	3-6
1.1	Research objectives	8
1.2	Rationale of the Study	8
1.3	Theoretical and Conceptual Framework	9
W2.	Research Questions	10
3.	Literature Review	11
4.	Research Gap	11
5.	Background of the study	12-16
6.	Research Methodology	17
7.	Research Findings	17
8.	Analog & Discussion	18-20
9.	Limitation	21
10.	Conclusion	21
11.	Acknowledgement	22
12.	References	22-23

1.1 Research Objectives

- To evaluate alienation, Social judgment or misjudgment , identity crisis in '*Daisy Miller*' and in '*The Catcher in the Rye*'.
- To analyze the portrayal of cultural disillusionment in *Daisy Miller* and in *The Catcher in the Rye* by Comparing European social codes and postwar American Society.

- To Explain the loosing of innocence in both texts examining Daisy's defiance of social norms and Holden's rejection of adult phoniness.
- To investigate how each protagonists journey in Europe and New York reflects Daisy as the "uncultured" outsider abroad and Holden as the disaffected insider at home.

1.2 Rationale of the Study

I read both text Daisy Miller, a novella and the Catcher in the Rye,, a novel very well from first line to last line. Cultural disillusionment, losing innocence, American identity abroad and at home are literary theories that I like most. For that reason, I have chosen the topic portraits of cultural disillusionment and loosing innocence.

A comparative study of American identity Abroad and at home, no one has worked on this topic before. This is also encouraged me to choose the topic.

1.3 Theoretical & Conceptual Framework

Existential crisis is feeling and self reflection, questioning, as well as about searching the meaning of life. Additionally searching the purpose of life, and the existence in nature. It often involves anxiety, confusion, triggered in isolation. Doubt about self belief, experiencing a near death or almost death, become faded from the world. The concept is deeply rooted in the philosophical movement in gained prominence in the 19th and 20th centuries. **Soren Kierkegaard** is widely considerate, the "father of existentialism" and a key figure for understanding the anxieties and uncertainties with questioning one's existence. He is a Danish philosopher, credited with laying the foundation for existential thought.

Nietzsche and Fyodor Dostoevsky are other influential figures in the framework about individuals a struggle. The term "existential crisis" itself, refers to the period of questioning and anxiety that can arise individual grapple with fundamental questions about the purpose of life and the world.

Conceptual terms stand in literature for its basic. I study, which is based on basics in the starting part, like it is present on plot of view, or sometimes represented as a summary of the story. Conceptual is consisting of or relating to concept. It is refers to scholarly articles or academic work, which provides the foundation or analyzing a particular phenomenon in the context. Another way, a conceptual framework reflects ideas of the underlying concept that the whole story describe.

The idea of conceptual framework is structured to organizing and understanding the story evolved overtime, drawing from various fields like theory, theme, motive, symbols, system, philosophical concept, and reasons. In research, Miles, Huberman and Saldana are known for their work on conceptual framework, it's importance in visualizing and understanding the relation between the key factors and concepts within a study. Particularly qualitative research Miles and Huberman in 1994, give their contribution to develop the conceptual framework. The conceptual framework is not the work of individual but rather a gradual process from different fields.

The novella Daisy Miller, and novel The Catcher in the Rye , two protagonist represent their existential identity in different ways, which is based on a conceptual term. Being a comparative study the existential workers with Daisy in Europe, as an American. She traveling this situation throw in abroad, by Mrs. Costello and Mrs. Walker. She is representing her culture, and she is a proud kid. Daisy changed by a dress, culture, style of leading life, talking sense with strangers and all above her innocence brutally misjudged.

On the other hand, holding in suffering from dilemma, traumatized boy. Holden being abused by his teacher as well. He does not need to go anywhere, while he's home misjudged him. As a comparative study, Holden also suffered from identity crisis in different way. The society made him adult and he is forced to lost his innocence.

2. Research Question

1. How do *Daisy Miller* and *The Catcher in the Rye* optimize the theme of navigating the transition from innocence to experience?
2. In what ways do *Daisy Miller* and *The Catcher in the Rye* express the essential crisis, social judgment, focusing on youth expressed?
3. How do *Daisy Miller* and *The Catcher in the Rye* reflect the failure of American idealism against European formality and post-war American conformity?
4. How does Henry James criticize exaggerated age American naivety abroad while J.D. Salinger criticizes post-war American hypocrisy at home in *The Catcher in the Rye*?

3. Literature Review

In his paper *Sisters Choice* Elaine Showalter interprets Daisy as the Embodiment of the naive but independent American girl. She argues that Daisy's behavior reflects not moral looseness but a cultural freshness that clashes with rigid European high class standards. According to Showalter, Daisy's death symbolized the cost of remaining innocent in a society that demands conformity and codes of conduct. As a result, I also found that Daisy being forced to be an European, where she took as an uncultured girl, because she is pure and authentic American representative. (E. Showalter, 1992)

According to Geoffrey Walton, he observes that Daisy Miller is a "portrait of the outsider" struggling against a rigid and often hypocritical society. Walton emphasizes that Daisy's alienation stems from the cultural clash between American innocence and European experience. In my research similarly This paper found Daisy's struggling as a outsider in Europe and she was criticized by Mrs Costallo and Mrs Walker. They were also the reason for losing Daisy's innocence the breakdown of emotions. (G.Walton, 1969)

Sarah way Sherman, notes that Daisy identity is never Self defined but always seen through the eyes of other peoples. She views Daisy as a victim of a society that refuses her freedom, However I also notices the struggle of identity crisis of Daisy and European tried to create barrier in her freedom. She trapped between being the flirt and the innocent. (S.W. Sarah, 1981)

James Bryan portrayed that Holden coalfield suffered adolescent crisis of identity that is marked by confusion, fear and innocence. This paper also argue that Holden covered with fake double faced people around him. This novel emphasizing a spiritual journey centered on identity formation. (J. Bryan, 1960)

Elizabeth Frank's paper examines the alienation of Holden in the novel 'The Catcher in the Rye' deeply reflective of the postwar American youth's disillusionment with conformity. This research experiments the alienation, identity crisis in JD Salingers character Holden Caulfield. (E. Frank, 1976)

4. Research Gap

The research paper explores the gap of cultural disillusionment and the loss of innocence in *Daisy Miller* and *The Catcher in the Rye*, focusing on the protagonists' struggles with societal expectations, class distinctions, and the transition from childhood to adulthood. While the study effectively compares the two texts using qualitative methods and literary theories such as alienation, identity crisis, and cultural conflict. It leaves several gaps that could be addressed in future research because there are lack of multidimensional analysis. I try to find out limited exploration of psychological in depth. The paper touches on Holden's depression and Daisy's misjudgment by society, also it engage with psychological theories such as trauma or criticism to analyze their mental states more rigorously. A deep psychological examination enhance understanding of their loss of innocence. The research compares themes and investigates how they losing their innocence and suffering from cultural disillusionment in different ways. *The Catcher in the Rye & Daisy Miller* shape the reader's perception of innocence and disillusionment. The study remains confined to historical literary analysis without connecting these themes to modern day issues of adolescent alienation, cultural displacement, or societal expectations. Future research could explore how these 19th and 20th-century narratives resonate with today's youth in the context of social media, globalization, and evolving cultural norms.

5. Background of the Study

Daisy Miller is reflection of Henry James famous work and literary toast of London and it appeared in "The Cornhill Magazine, as a series in June-July 1878. The Cornhill Magazine was a monthly Victorian magazine and literary journal named after the street address of the founding publisher Smith, Elder & Co. at 65 Cornhill in London. Daisy Miller is a novella. The major theme of this novella is individual liberty and the transition from innocence to experience of the protagonist by the tyrannical society. Henry James often illustrate the American and European societies in his novella and how the societal norms affected negatively in the individual characters psychologically, as well as expatriate American abroad in Europe.

Daisy Miller is a complete and unabridged novella by Henry James, widely regarded as one of his most beloved works. In this enduring classic, James draws one of his most captivating heroines who is Daisy Miller, a young woman including honesty, vivacious, and charmingly flirtatious, yet whose free spirit nature clashes with the rigid expectations of high society like Europe.

In the hinder place in the wealthy holidays resorts, Americans hang on to their old ways and traditions. Daisy Miller, with her strong honesty and innocence of mind, is anathema to them. Even to Winterbourne, the young American student whom she meets on the Shores of Lake Geneva, although she is 'uncultivated' and captivated by him. He feels that she is a little and too forward for polite society. At the heart of this timeless masterpiece lies the contrast between Daisy's delighting naivety and Winterbourne's hesitant a dynamic decision that continues to captivate readers.

The novel is divided into four chapters in the first chapter, whole story based on Veyvey. Frederick Winterbourne is an American living in Geneva since long for his studies. He visits Veyvey to meet his widow aunt Mrs. Costello, who is wealthy and she is having a headache. Winterbourne goes to hotel Trois Couronnes to visit the grand Hotel in the hotel he meets with an enthusiastic nine years old and brother of Daisy Miller who is Randolph Miller. Daisy is the protagonist of the novella. Randolph talks to Winterbourne, with full confidence, and he realizes that the boy is an American. Randolph introduces winter world with Daisy. He's too impressed by daisies, innocence and beauty because she is direct and honest with her beauty. She doesn't take interest in winter one, but talk with him beautifully when he talks about the beautiful sights of Veyvey and then she starts talking interestingly. At one, Perth Winterbourne proposes that he took Randolph and Daisy to visit the "old castle" and

Daisy agrees where Winterbourne finds Daisy is very innocent and frank. However, Randolph doesn't want to go. So Winterbourne suggesting that he would take Daisy to someone who may vouch for her and he is as good as well as trustworthy and she can go with him alone.

In chapter two, later on Winterbourne meets his aunt Mrs. Costello and asks her about the newly arrived Miller family. His aunt is reputed member of American expert society of Europe. She tells that Daisy is a common girl of low class and she doesn't like her much and she also doesn't approve her mother and Mrs. Miller and says that she's too dependent on the family servant Eugenio. Winterbourne tells her that he wants to meet with Daisy, but Mrs. Costello denies and tells him to remain away from Daisy. She also portrays that Daisy is a flirt and uncultured girl. However, Winterbourne protest straightforwardly on the favor of Daisy's innocence and tells that her innocence is natural and she is unaware of European customs. He meets Daisy the very same night when she was walking with her mother, Mrs. Miller was too preoccupied with all things. Daisy tells her mother about the outing plan with Winterbourne. Although Winterbourne's aunt misjudged Daisy. However after two days Winterbourne take Daisy to Chillon on a steamer and she is not embarrassed. Winterbourne hope it will be a romantic visit, but he finds Daisy boring and grave. In that moment, the loss of innocence is fully focused. Anyways, Winterbourne tells Daisy that he will go Rome very soon and meet her. He promises to Daisy his words.

Chapter three in Rome Winterbourne get news through Mrs. Costello's letter that Daisy has made many third rate Italian male friends. In the case of protest winter one thing that Miller just ignores European customs, but he finds Daisy is innocent. Then he visit Mrs. Walker another American. He knows since years. He arranges a meet with Daisy at Mrs. Walker's house. After meeting Daisy portrays that he broke promise as he didn't came to visit her in Rome. Daisy's mother doesn't like Rome that much but Daisy want to be a part of the high class society. So Mrs. Walker invite Daisy to her party. Instantly, Daisy asked if she could bring her friend Mrs. Giovanelli to her party too and Mrs. Walker agrees. After finishing the party, Mrs. Walker spread rumors about Daisy that she's getting close to low class Italian man especially juvenile. Winter Barney meets Giovanni and he appears a gentleman. He wonders about Daisy that how she gets close to juvenile, while she is so innocent and good to him. He and Mrs. Walker try hard to keep Daisy away from Giovanelli, but she doesn't listen to them. Gradually, Daisy becomes misjudged by them and lost her innocence. Mrs. Miller continues to ignore the issue about Daisy's misjudgment.

Lastly, chapter four, Winterbourne believes that Miller family is just uncultivated and unaware of the Roman customs. Besides Mrs. Walker declares that she will never allow Daisy in her home. Everyone also tells that, Daisy is a 'flirt'. Daisy accepts that she is a flirt and says that she will never change. Furthermore, happening that all of a sudden winter burn wants to meet with Daisy because he cannot forget her prettiness and innocence. He couldn't say that he is in love with Daisy. He get jealous when he saw that, Daisy is sitting alone with Giovanelli in the hotel. One day he saw that Geovanelli and Daisy in the Colosseum at night at scolding Giovanelli for taking risk of the epidemic fever with Daisy. On that moment, he feels that Daisy do not deserve his respect and he leaves. After some days, Daisy got ill and die. Winterbourne feels criminal to himself after talking with Giovanelli that Daisy was only just friend of Giovanelli.. He feels later that, his first idea of Daisy being an innocent girl was right. He realizes that maybe he is also responsible for the death of Daisy. On that note, Daisy being experienced from childhood to adulthood. The next summer, when Winterbourne went to visit his aunt Mrs. Costello, he also told to his aunt that he did injustice to Daisy.

Analysis, Daisy Miller, novella's characters, Frederick Winterbourne is a young American man who is twenty seven years old. Also spent a lot of time in Europe. He was educated in Geneva. Letter proofs as the bitterness of tragic failure, and become more resident than tourist. He is the type of Europeanized

expatriate that Mrs. Costello and Mrs. Walker also represent. In many ways, he is a central character as Daisy and suddenly the novella's central consciousness. Because through his character, we experience everything. Early on, he is "addicted to observing and analyzing" feminine beauty, but doesn't appear to be discriminating thinker. He was in confusion into Daisy's innocence and unable to judge correctly her before her death. He defends Daisy in many terms. Later on, he felt guilt after the death of Daisy and told his aunt that he did great injustice against Daisy.

Daisy Miller, the original name of her is Annie P. Miller, American girl traveling through Europe with her mother and brother. Daisy is the protagonist of the novella. Authentic and pure American girl in Europe misjudged by Mrs. Costello and Mrs. Walker. She lost her innocence in Europe by Europeans and also become experienced. Her humor spreads about her that, she has made low class Italian male friend, like her friend Mr. Giovanelli. Winterbourne likes her innocence and get jealous when he saw her with Giovanelli. At the end of the novella, Daisy accepts that she is a flirt. Because, others titled her "flirtatious" girl and "uncultured" as well. Psychologically, she wants to protect her family from the rumors, as she is become a victim by the Europeans. The initial part shows that Daisy's transition from innocence to experience as well as she become misjudged, suffering from cultural disillusionment in American in abroad, also suffering from identity crisis.

Randolph Miller, a nine years old, young boy, and brother of Daisy Miller. He was eating a candy while meet with Frederick Winterbourne. He's an American. He is impudent also shocks the American expatriates. He likes American because his dad was there. But he is hyperbolic patriotic serves a reminder of ignorant pride about the country. James thinks Americans are guilty. The boy only nine years, is also misused by Europeans.

Mrs. Miller and American mother of Daisy and Randolph. She seems to except her children's behavior in a sorts of resigned. And less strict woman, never cares about her children, when the remorse prays about Daisy. She don't even give any kind of attention. As an American mother, she love her children, but never wants deep to their hearts. As a result, here, focused that an industrialization, transforming family life.

Mrs. Costello, European wealthy widow, lived in Europe. She is a aunt of Winterbourne. She is belong from high society and a quick judgmental woman. She never likes Daisy, being pure and authentic American. From her perspective, she believes that Miller family is a "nouveau riche" means newly reach, because they have lack of money before. This judge came from staying at hotel in Europe. On the other hand, she told Daisy an uncultured, depends on her stress and she portrait that Europeans are sophisticated. Mrs. Costello is the reason of daisies, losing innocence, breakdown of emotion as well, also suffering from cultural disillusionment.

Mrs. Walker, another woman known for since years by Winterbourne in Rome. When she invited Daisy in the party, though Daisy wants to be a part of high society, was misused by her and she spreads rumor about Daisy. Daisy asked her if she could bring her friend Mr. Giovanelli with her. For that reason, she become victim and innocence properly here and she being experienced.

Mr. Giovanelli, a gentleman live in Rome. He is a friend of Daisy Miller. Because of attending the party with Daisy, he also misjudged by Mrs. Walker. At the end of the novella, Winterbourne comes to know that he is a just friend of Daisy after her death.

The Catcher in the Rye by JD Salinger is the ultimate novel for disaffected youth. It is published in 1951, is coming of each novel set in the post World War II, specially in the late 1940s or early 1950s. The story primarily unfold in two locations, in Pency Prep and New York City. Pency Prep represents

the breakdown of emotion, innocence, and Phoniness of Holden and New York City presents backdrop for his emotional turmoil and search for authenticity.

The novel is told by Holden Caulfield, a seventeen years old dropout who has just been kicked out of his fourth school. Throughout, Holden dissects the 'phony' aspects of society, and the phonies themselves; the headmaster whose concern depends on the wealth of the parents, his roommate, who scores with curls using sickly sweet affection. It is a novel full of slang and swear words, whose interest and appeal comes from its observation rather than its plot intrigues. Salinger's style creates an effect of conversation, it is as Holden is speaking to you personally as through you too have seen through the presence of the American Dramas and growing up unable to see the point of living in the society around you.

Autobiographical elements of literature are the fundamental components that make up any story. The novel is Semi autobiographical novel while Salinger's own life and experiences including fictionalized events and characters. It is not presented as a fictional account, while based on real life. The protagonist's childhood mirrors the authors own life.

The Catcher in the Rye, is divided into twenty six part and each part told the single events of protagonist's life. firstly holder beans narrating his history from Pency Prep. He is present at boarding school and being expelled due to poor academic performance, especially failing four out of five subjects. At the school he has fight with Stradlater, his roommate for a girl named Jane Gallagher. The reason behind it was, Holden like Jane and she go to date with Stradlater. Mr. & Mrs. Spencer are well wisher of Holden. He leaves Pency Prep wanders New York City for three days and avoids his parents. Instead of waiting until Wednesday, Holden takes a train to New York City. Then he reaches to the Edmont hotel, also observe people around him as well. He considers the people there as fake and double face. He wants to connect with people, but failed as he is younger. On the contrary, he went to a bar and he awkwardly dancing with three women there for getting relief from reminisce of Jane. After that, he met with a woman named Sunny in a prostitute and he hires her through Maurice, the operator of Edmont hotel. Holden initial you want to get touch with her physically in room number 1222 but does not, because he lost his interest. At one point, innocence breakdown here properly and he become misjudged by the society. Holden has only his sister he love most, name Phoebe, 10 years old. He only tells her that, what he wants to do in his life. He imagines himself as the guardian who save his children from falling off a cliff. He visits his former English teacher, Mr. Antolini who wants him and heading for a physical collapse. Holden woke up to find that his teacher is painting his head.

Holden hastily excuses himself and leaves. After that he sleeping for a few hours on a bench at Grand Central Station. Holden goes to Phoebe's school and sends her a note that meet him in the lunch time. Actually Holden was facing trauma, mental disillusionment again and again. For that, he is leaving home. When Phoebe arrives, she is carrying a suitcase full of clothes and ask Holden to take her with him. But he refuses her, and walk away. He know that she will follow him, so he walks to the Zoo and then takes her across the park to console her. Then buys tickets and watches her ride it. Suddenly starts to rain so heavily. Holden is so happy to watching his sister write the carousel that he is close to tears. lastly he decides to go to a new school in the fall and cautiously optimistic about his future. There he shows us that, how he becomes so protective to his sister. Psychologically, he makes balance that he should protect his sister, so that she will never faces the incident as Holden has face. Furthermore, Holden grows up from innocence to adulthood, in fact he get experienced,. He is misjudged by the people at home and the reason behind his loosing of innocence is the society around him.

Holden Caulfield, the protagonist and the novel narrator as well. He is 17 years old and send him to the boarding school in very early age. He has been expelled for academic failure from his school. His

parents portrait as emotionally, distant and neglectful, contributing to his feelings of alienation and isolation. Their lack of engagement with Holden, make him traumatized. After, his brother Eli's death they leave him feeling unsupported and misunderstood. The parental shapes makes his behavior much more aggressive. The lack of emotional support from his parents leads Holden to feel isolation and disconnected from others. He represent pure American-parenting role in nineteenth century. Holden is purely and authentically representing American culture. He also break his innocence. The obvious sign that Holden is a troubled and unreliable narrator. All the things happened or cause from jealousy. Holden loves his sister, Phoebe is honest and he only trust her. The world is against Holden, but he is happy to see his sister, while she is riding. She is the one who is honest, simple and love Holden very much. Phoebe understands that growing up is a necessary process being only 10 years old. She also understands that Holden's refusal to take her with him to mature reveals less about the outside world then it does about himself.

Phoebe Caulfield, 10 years old, beloved sister of the protagonist Holden Caulfield. He loves her dearly. Though she is 10 years old, but she listened to her brother what he says, and understands him more than others people do. Holden's happiness depends on her sister, because she's the source of his happiness. Only, she who is honest and natural to hold in. At times, she shows great maturity to Holden. The world will also trying to misjudged her, but Holden being a protector of her. Although Phoebe, being a part of support of Holden, as well as loves him much than others.

Stradlater, a roommate of Holden Caulfield in Pency Prep at boarding school. Holden calls him a 'secret slob'. His presence in the novel serves to highlight some of Holden's psychological issues. Physical attachment become interesting for him. Holden does not like him because he went to date with the girl who holding like very much named Jane. Stradlater has lack of personality.

Mr. Antolini, Holden's former English teacher at the Elkton Hills School. Now he teaches at New York University. He has fake face also. Because, when Holden went to him for getting sympathy, he drinks heavily and wants to make with Holden physical relationship. A Student always learn good from his teacher, but here, Mr. Antolini keeps two faces with Holden. He is good at outside and internally. He is abuse a child like Holden. Although he is a child abuser. In that initial part child abusing portraits perfectly by a teacher, Mr. Antolini.

6. Research Methodology

This research paper follows qualitative research method. Qualitative research is concerned with quality of information. Qualitative research method attempts to gain an understanding of the underlying reasons and motivations for actions and established how people interpret their experience and the world around them. This method allows the respondent to talk in some depth, choosing their own words. I have been collected my information from two type of sources. The first one is primary source of information and next one is secondary source of information. This paper is discussed by reading both novella and novel again and again as a primary source of information. Paper book, journal reports and web sites are used to obtain extra data as a secondary source of information. As this research paper is processed in a comparative way, man literary theories are also used to complete the task. Alienation identity crisis, social judgement teenagers disillusionment with phoniness and cultural clashes are the theory that are used to analysis the topic.

Moreover watching YouTube videos and some kind of strong tutorials helps researchers to obtain extra information as a secondary source of information. Here data has been analyzed in using comparative and contrastive approach alienation existential crisis social judgement, teenagers disillusionment with phoniness and cultural conflict to reach a conclusion.

7. Research Findings

From the survey I found the Cultural Disillusionment while I searched it into the novella *Daisy Miller and The catcher in the Rye* in a different ways. Furthermore, both protagonist have a fiction and they also faced the challenges where they loose their innocence and get experienced from childhood to adulthood .The theme of navigating the transition from innocence to experience is found into both texts. The identity crisis and social judgments are often based upon class diction, other one is questioned in a boy's childhood, who becomes abused. Both protagonist have faced difficulties by questioning in their youth. My research survey shows the reflection on how the American idealism against European formality and post-war American conformity which I found while studying both texts. James criticize exaggerated age American naivety abroad in *Daisy Miller* while J.D. Salinger criticizes post-war American hypocrisy at home in *The Catcher in the Rye*. James criticized as a social experiment by the character Daisy and Salinger criticized Industrial Revolution as well as the boy's sufferings at his home. As a result, the study finds cultural disillusionment , loosing childhood innocence and socially misjudged by Daisy and Holden.

8. Analysis and Discussion

Cultural Disillusionment and loosing innocence, identity crisis are present in both text. Cultural disillusionment is considered the new type of way about loosing innocence and suffering from identity crisis as well. It is mentions in the both text that both protagonist rare reject social norms, experience deep isolation and criticized on cultural expectations. Daisy struggles with old world prejudices, while Holden's struggles with the moral decay of his own society. Daisy tragedy highlights the sufferings of cultural misunderstanding, while Holden is a sufferer of breakdown of mentally, emotionally. Daisy is unaware of how her behavior is perceived by European, but Holden clings to childhood purity but has forced to confront adult corruption

"She is very charming, but how deucedly sociable!"

(Henry James,1878, Chapter – I)

These lines comes from Henry James novella 1878. The lines is suggesting the American vs. European cultural clash. Winterbourne in his first meet of Daisy, was very charming, but when the cultural rigidly and social hypocrisy attack by the misjudge of culture by Mrs Costello, it creates bias. Here creates confusion in Winterbourne about Daisy. American freedom and European rigidity fail to understand one another and often reveals tragic events. Although Winterbourne struggles internally also feels the pull of social conditions. Though he sees Daisy so friendly as a stranger.

**"They are very common,
They are the sort of Americans that one does one's duty by not accepting"**

(Henry James, 1878, Chapter – II)

Here, winterbourne's aunt Mrs. Costello represents European culture and neglecting Millers family. She see Daisy as a vulgar and creating cultural barriers. She also focused on self work, that Miller family always did their work by servant rather than do it by own. In the case of European, they did their work by own. Cultural discrimination reflects here by the lines, which is portrait in the novella by Mrs. Costello.

"She is completely uncultured"

(Henry James, 1878, Chapter – II)

Mrs Costello is a wealthy, upper class American living in Europe. She is very conscious of social status. When Winterbourne offers her to meet with Daisy, she denies, because Daisy is low class girl and not fitting in European society according to her perspective. Cultural conflict focuses here by the word uncultivated. She also claim that Daisy is 'tremendous flirt' and Miller family is newly rich as well. The term 'uncultured' ironically reveals into the novella and also the part of misjudgment of the character Daisy. It shows that, how society can misunderstand or destroy innocence of any child.

**" I am not afraid of anything,
I don't care what people say"**

(Henry James, 1878, Chapter – II)

Daisy is proud of her culture which is American, pride to represent it as well. Above lines said by Daisy through the novella. European wants to settled down Daisy and make her according to their culture. Later failed, because she never care of anyone's lame talking. Daisy thinks that makings of male friend is not about doing flirt. On the other hand, talking beautifully with other people is not flirtatious behavior. To some extent, Winterbourne protest for Daisy with his aunt.

**"When then would he have proposed change to her to walk?
The Pincio is not the streets either; and I thank goodness
am not a young lady of this country.
The young country of this country have a dreadfully poky time of it,
so far as I can learn; I don't see why I should change my habits for them."**

(Henry James, 1878, Chapter-IV)

Daisy said this line to Winterbourne, while he told her to change her habits. He claim that Daisy is also a flirt. Mrs Walker when spreads rumors to Winterbourne about Daisy and her friend, Mrs Giovanelli when they join the party and he takes Daisy as a flirt and being sorry that he can't dance. Though European people has different idea, but he is also like them in thinking. In that case, for him it would be have been most unkind that he had been talking about his and Daisy's walk for ten days. Daisy rejects to changed her habit for silly things. Although she said this country ladies has poky time and there in nothing can be learned from them.

**"I am a fearful, frightful flirt!
Did you ever hear of a nice girl that was not?
But I suppose you will tell me now that I am not a nice girl."**

(Henry James, 1878, Chapter-IV)

In that initial lines, Daisy being rude with Winterbourne while he calls Daisy flirt. Daisy's self description highlights her innocence. European doing misjudge about Daisy. As a result she admits that she is a flirt. On the contrary, here can be focused psychological concepts. The reason behind it, she has a family and she never wants that her family will ever faced this situation. After saying that lines of Daisy, Winterbourne said her that, he wish if Daisy would flirt with him and only with him. Daisy claim that he can misjudged and tell her that she is not a nice girl anymore.

"Life is a game boy. Life is a game that one plays according to the rules."

(JD Salinger, 1951, Chapter-II)

The quote portrait by Mr Spencer, Holden's history teacher. This is too significant because it describes the social expectations that Holden rebels against. Because he is suffocating from conformity and structure. His history teacher is represent the adults perspective of the world and told that life is competition and the success depends on social norms. On the other hand, Holden rejects the idea and break the rules as phoniness. His refusal leads to his isolation.

Contrast with his later realization at the carousel in chapter twenty five.

"The thing with kids is if they want to grab for the gold ring you have to let them do it"

Holden is accepted the risk of failure as a part of growth. Post WWII American culture empathized disillusionment and breakdown the era's of teenagers rebellion, which is later seen in 1960s. Holden accepts that he should grow up even no matter if its hurt though. His loss of innocence focused here. Another breakdown of innocence is when the fight happens between Stradlater and Holden, then Holden being a smoker.

"People always clap for the wrong things."

(JD Salinger, 1951, Chapter – III)

Holden give a thought on that , people has shallow admiration for fame and successes. Being a seventeen year boy, he criticizes adulthood as well, being corrupt and he reject the war and aggression Contrast with patriotism.

"I don't know what I was running for I guess just felt like it."

(JD Slinger, 1951, Chapter- I)

The lines symbolizes Holden's aimlessness and confusion. Holden misjudged at home in America. The reason behind it is, the parenting role of Holden's parents. He doesn't need to go anywhere in Contrast with Daisy from Daisy Miller. He lost his identity at home. His aggressive behavior reflects his instability, self awareness of his phoniness, isolation and feeling disconnected from everyone around him.

"I'd just be the Catcher in the rye and all.

I know it's crazy, but that's the only thing I'd really like to be . I know its crazy."

(JD Salinger, 1951, Chapter- 25)

This last quote and one of the most famous from The Catcher in the Rye, Holden describes a dream to his sister, that he will always carried with him. He states that, he would like to stand in such a field, where he can saves all the children who are on their way to adulthood. He would catch them and prevent them from having the same experience as he has having. He had experienced all his way from loosing childhood to adulthood with a terrible journey. To some extent, he lost himself in physical needs, he became drunk and all and now he cope up with the horrible journey of him and vow to stands with the children who are in the way of their adulthood and save them from all terrible journey he has.

9. Limitations

There are many barriers to conduct research from Bangladeshi perspective. Though Bangladesh have a rich library where one can do in depth research. Due to insufficient time I couldn't go into the depth of research maybe but from my sides I read both of the book from the first to last line. Lack of sources about the research is not sufficient to prove it perfectly but I made it as a comparative study. I read many paper on different topic related to the texts, collect their research and opinion and I added some of my perspective to showcase the comparative study by myself.

10. Conclusion

Daisy Miller, and The Catcher in the Rye, demonstrates largely with cultural disillusionment with identity, crisis and losing innocence. The endings of both texts give a different impact to the readers as the suffering are same, but the way of suffering is different. The study of both texts equally reviews, cultural disillusionment, losing innocence and identity crisis true characterization, and comparative study. Henry James shape Daisy Miller, his novella around cultural crisis, misjudgment by another country people as they are wealthy. This novella discussed the cultural conflict and class distinction of a young girl. The study illustrate how a young girl being experienced from childhood to adulthood. The study discussed about losing innocence at abroad in America, the suffering and misjudgment of a girl and Her cruel moment which is finished in her death. Only a good friendship with a male friend and talking nicely with a stranger making her character rough. On the other hand, JD Salinger structures his novel The Catcher in the Rye, a boy who is traumatized at his home. The study evaluates, losing innocence of a boy who is going to be abused by his teacher as well as depressed. The lack of guidance of parents make him experience from childhood to adulthood. In his way of terrible journey, he decided to prevent preventing those children's who are the way of their adulthood. At the end, the sentence " I want to stay catcher in the rye" reflect the corruption of the society and the strongest of seventeen years old boy.

Acknowledgement

From my personal experience, I can say that it is almost impossible for anyone not to feel miserable or frustrated at one point or another while writing a thesis. The thesis is certainly an endeavor that cannot take place on its own. It is an amalgamation of hard work critical thinking, and sleepless night that can yield the desired outcome only with the assistance and encouragement of different people to facilitate the successful computation of the thesis.

My first and foremost, thanks to go the Almighty for enabling me to complete this research. Then my sincerest gratitude goes to my supervisor Afsana Afrose Moon Ma'am, for these invaluable suggestions, assistance and guidance while writing this paper. I should also mention the mental support that she provided me during my thesis and once again proved that a supervisor or a teacher is not just an educator, but also a guide, a counselor and certainly a facilitator. Also the head of the English department Naima Afrin , the honorable dean Syeda Afsana Ferdousi, Tania Tabassum, Shuvo Das, Md.Saiful Islam sir and madam, all others who helped me in different ways by giving me suggestion and directions. There instrumental support, lectures, and guidelines that I enjoyed in their course works in the last four years have undoubtedly shaped my thoughts that I hope will continue to do so.

I also recall my classmates and friends for their cordial and constant support also for tolerating my strange temperament while writing this thesis.

To the University authorities and teachers for allowing me to conduct the survey which was required for the successful completion of this paper.

11. Reference

Showalter, E. (1992). Daisy as the embodiment of the naïve but independent American girl. *Edith Wharton's House of Mirth*, 9, 133–149.

Walton, G. (1950). Daisy Miller: A portrait of the outsider. *The Cambridge Journal*, 4, 172–187.
Sherman, S. W. (1981). Daisy's identity is never self-defined but always seen through the eyes of other people. *The New England Quarterly*, 54(3), 387–404.

Bryan, J. (1974). Holden Caulfield's adolescent identity crisis in *The Catcher in the Rye*. *PMLA*, 89(5), 1065–1074.

Frank, E. (1985). The alienation of Holden in *The Catcher in the Rye*. *The Sewanee Review*, 93(4), 553–567.

Dizdar, S., & Toker, A. (2012). Holden Caulfield: Alien in *The Catcher in the Rye*. *Dil ve Edebiyat Eğitimi Dergisi*, 1(2), 71–82.

Ball, M. (2018). The liminal time of friendship: Narrative delay in Hannah Webster Foster's *The Coquette*. In K. J. Jacobson et al. (Eds.), *Liminality, hybridity, and American women's literature: Thresholds in women's writing* (pp. 57–76). Palgrave Macmillan.

Bartlett, A., et al. (2019). *Flirting in the era: Negotiating intimacy*. Springer International.

Beckham, S. B. (2006). The American front porch: Women's liminal space. In B. M. Lane (Ed.), *Housing and dwelling: Perspectives on modern domestic architecture* (pp. 86–94).

Home, A., & Family. (1991). *Stories and society: Children's literature in its social context*. Macmillan. (pp. 37–49).

Clark, B. L. (2003). *Kiddie lit: The cultural construction of children's literature in America*. Johns Hopkins University Press.